

**"The Influence of Organizational Climate on Employees'
Organizational Citizenship Behavior: A Case Study of the
Ministry of Agriculture in Hargeisa, Somaliland"**

BY:

MOHAMED O. IBRAHIM

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DECLARATION

I, Mohamed Osman Ibrahim, hereby declare that the research presented in this thesis, represents my original work and has been undertaken in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of a Master's degree of Human Resource Management.

To the best of my knowledge and belief, the findings, analyses, and conclusions contained herein have not been previously submitted, published, or presented in any form for another academic qualification or publication. All sources of information, data, and intellectual contributions by other authors referenced in this thesis have been duly cited and acknowledged in compliance with established academic standards and ethical guidelines.

DEDICATION

This research is dedicated to my beloved parents, whose unwavering support, encouragement, and sacrifices have been a constant source of inspiration throughout my academic journey.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CSSP- Civil Service Strengthening Project

DV – Dependent Variable

ERB - Extra-Role Behavior

ICT - Information Communications Technology

IV- independent Variable

MOA – Ministry of Agriculture

NASP - National Agriculture Strategic Plan

OC – Organization Climate

OCB - Organizational citizenship behavior

SPSS - Statistical Package for Social Scientists

ABSTRACT

Organizational climate represents employees' collective perceptions of their work environment, encompassing shared attitudes, beliefs, and values that shape workplace dynamics. Meanwhile, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) refers to voluntary, discretionary actions that employees undertake beyond their formal job descriptions, contributing to overall organizational effectiveness. In public institutions across Somaliland, including the Ministry of Agriculture (MOA), fostering a positive organizational climate is essential for enhancing employee motivation, engagement, and performance. However, a persistent gap in OCB among public-sector employees, particularly within the MOA, has impeded the timely achievement of institutional goals.

This study aimed to assess the prevailing levels of OCB and organizational climate within the MOA, examine the relationship between these two constructs, and determine the extent to which organizational climate influences OCB. A quantitative cross-sectional research design was employed, utilizing a census approach to collect data from all 95 MOA employees through a structured questionnaire.

The findings revealed that both OCB and organizational climate at the MOA were relatively low (Overall Mean = 1.93, indicating a low level). Additionally, a strong, positive, and statistically significant correlation was observed between organizational climate and OCB ($r = 0.847$, $p < 0.001$). Multiple regression analysis identified key organizational climate factors—specifically, organizational goals, rewards, and effective communication—as significant drivers of OCB, highlighting their critical role in shaping employee behavior.

The study concludes that a well-structured and supportive organizational climate is essential for fostering OCB among employees. Accordingly, it is recommended that public institutions, particularly the MOA, prioritize HRM strategies that enhance organizational climate, including clear goal-setting, transparent communication, and equitable reward systems. Strengthening these elements will not only improve OCB but also enhance employee commitment, productivity, and overall institutional effectiveness.

Keywords: *Organizational climate, organizational citizenship behavior, Ministry of Agriculture*

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 Introduction

This chapter entails the background of the study, the problem statement, the objectives, significance of the study, scope, conceptual framework and the definition of important terms.

1.1 Background of the study

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is a concept that has been studied extensively in the field of organizational behavior. Organ (1988) defined OCB as the behavior employees exhibit at work place though not dictated by any rules or due to rewards. He further mentioned that this behavior promotes the general effectiveness and functioning of an organization. It refers to behaviors that are beyond the formal job requirements but contribute to the organization's success (Podsakoff et al., 2000).

The concept of OCB was first introduced by Organ and his colleagues in the 1980s (Yao et al., 2011). Organ argued that OCB is a multi-dimensional construct that has behavioral, personal, and official nature, which is not explicitly recognized by the organization's reward systems but promotes the organization's performance and efficiency (Appelbaum et al., 2004; Hall et al., 2009).

Organizational climate is another important concept that has been studied extensively in the field of organizational behavior. The earliest reference to the concept of organizational climate can be traced back to 1939 as "Social Climate" by Lewin, Lippitt, & White (Srivastav, 2009). Organizational climate refers to employees' shared perceptions of their work environment, including attitudes, beliefs, and values. Schneider Benjamin (1973) described climate as "an individual's view of his work environment." According to (William H.Glick (1985), the climate construct adds value to organizational and individual behavior.

The relationship between organizational climate and OCB has been extensively studied in the literature (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Employees' engagement in OCB is influenced by the organizational climate (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Employees are encouraged to voluntarily go above and beyond their formal and core job obligations by engaging in OCB (Organ & Ryan, 1995).

A positive work environment and atmosphere encourage employees to be motivated and perform well (Carlos-Alegre, 2005). Managers play a crucial role in creating a positive work environment

and developing excellent working relationships with employees, which is essential for the organization's success (McGregor, 2005).

Understanding the relationship between organizational climate and OCB of public institution employees in Somaliland is important for the management and the organization's performance. In Somaliland, the public institutions have been undergoing a process of transformation over the years. The country has been recovering from decades of conflict, which has led to the establishment of new public institutions and reforms in the existing ones. Therefore, it is essential to examine the impact of the organizational climate on employees' engagement in OCB in the context of Somaliland.

Several studies have been conducted on the relationship between organizational climate and OCB in different contexts. For example, a study conducted by Chen et al. (2017) found that organizational climate has a positive impact on employees' engagement in OCB in the Chinese context. Similarly, a study conducted by Kiewitz et al. (2016) found that the positive relationship between organizational climate and OCB is stronger in organizations with a high level of collectivism.

Moreover, studies have shown that various factors influence the organizational climate and employees' engagement in OCB. For example, a study conducted by Kim et al. (2019) found that leadership style and job satisfaction have a significant impact on employees' engagement in OCB. Similarly, a study conducted by Adi et al. (2019) found that organizational culture has a significant impact on employees' engagement in OCB. The relationship between organizational climate and OCB of public institution employees in Somaliland is essential to understand the factors that influence positive employee behavior.

Previous studies have highlighted the importance of organizational climate in promoting OCB. For example, Podsakoff et al. (2000) found that employees' engagement in OCB is influenced by the organizational climate. Similarly, Carlos-Alegre (2005) argues that a positive work environment and atmosphere encourage employees to be motivated and perform well. Additionally, managers play a crucial role in creating a positive work environment and developing excellent working relationships with employees, which is essential for the organization's success (McGregor, 2005).

1.2 Statement of the problem

Public institutions in Somaliland operate in a complex and dynamic environment where they must deliver services efficiently and effectively to meet the needs of the citizens. To achieve this, public

institutions require motivated and committed employees who engage in behaviors that promote the effective functioning of the organization beyond their formal job requirements. Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is critical for achieving this goal, as it contributes to the organization's success (Podsakoff, et.al, 2000).

However, the existing organizational climate fails to create an optimal working atmosphere for the employees. Based on my extensive tenure as a civil servant over the past ten years, it has come to my attention that there appears to be a notable gap in organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among public-sector workers. In general, employees working in government organizations tend to exhibit a lack of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The staff of the Ministry of Agriculture has been having a deficiency in their level of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). I have selected the Ministry of Agriculture as my research focus due to my extensive three-year stay and substantial personal experience within the ministry, which provides sufficient evidence to support my claim.

There is also a literature gap when it comes to the influence of organizational climate on organizational citizenship behavior of the employees of public institutions in Somaliland. This research will be useful to public institutions, government agencies, and other researchers, research institutions and academic professionals at large. Therefore, there is a pressing need to investigate the relationship between organizational climate and OCB in public institutions in Somaliland, with a particular focus on the case of the Somaliland Ministry of Agriculture in Hargeisa. This study will aim to identify the factors that contribute to a positive work environment and encourage positive employee behavior, ultimately leading to increased organizational effectiveness. Addressing this gap in knowledge will benefit public institutions in Somaliland by providing managers with evidence-based insights to develop effective strategies that promote OCB and organizational climate.

To promote OCB, it is essential to create a positive work environment, also known as organizational climate. The work environment of public institutions in Somaliland is often challenging, with limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and weak governance structures. As a result, employees may not be motivated to engage in OCB, leading to reduced organizational effectiveness (Muse, 2021)

1.3 Research Objectives

General Objectives

This study aims to investigate the influence of organizational climate on organizational citizenship behaviors of the employees of public institutions, a case study of Somaliland Ministry of Agriculture in Hargeisa, Somaliland

1.5 Specific Objectives

1. To evaluate the level of organization climate and the organization citizenship behavior at MOA Hargeisa.
2. To determine the association between organization climate dimensions and the OCB of staff at the MOA.
3. To assess individual factors that affect OCB of the staff at MOA

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the level of organization climate and the organization citizenship behavior at MOA Hargeisa, Somaliland?
2. What is the association between organization climate dimensions and the OCB of staff at the MOA Hargeisa, Somaliland?
3. Does organizational climatic influence organizational citizenship behavior of employees at the ministry of Agriculture?

1.5 Scope of the study

Content Scope: This study will focus on organizational climate and organizational citizenship behaviors of the employees of Ministry of Agriculture in Hargeisa, Somaliland.

Geographical Scope: The geographical location of this study will be limited to the public institutions, especially Somaliland Ministry of Agriculture particularly in Hargeisa.

Time Scope: This study will be conducted between the months of January to July 2023.

1.6 Significance of the study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to the existing literature on OCB and organizational climate, particularly in the context of public institutions in Somaliland.

This research will be useful to public institutions, government agencies, and other researchers, research institutions and academic professionals.

institutions and academic professionals.

1.7 Operational definitions of key terms

"**Organizational climate** can be described, being a number of Measurable workplace qualities, which are either consciously or unconsciously experienced by individuals that inhabit and work in an area of work and are believed to impact their motivation and behavior. (Friedlander and Margulies (1969)

Organization: is an association of people who collaborate to attain a particular objective. (Drory, A., & Romm, T., 1990).

Citizenship: Citizenship is a character of individual viewed as member of the society behavior in term of the duties and obligations of citizen, they should require to abide by the laws of their country and defend themselves from their enemies, while the state gives special rights and privileges to its citizens (Morrison, D, 1999).

Behavior: The manner in which a person engages with other people (Ciocirlan, C. E, 2017).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior: the behavior employees exhibit at work place though not dictated by any rules or due to rewards (Organ, 1988).

Public institutions: A public institution is one that is under the authority of a governmental unit or over which a governmental agency has formal authority on it.

Ministry of Agriculture: is Somaliland Ministry of agricultural development charged by the state in developing and implementing agriculture sector policies, rules, and regulations, developing agricultural sector plans and projects, documenting and registering agricultural land, and conducting agricultural research.

1.8 Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework of this study shows the influence and the relationship between IV (Organizational Climate) and the DV (Citizenship Behavior).

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter contains the theoretical framework, empirical review and summary of literature review

2.1 Theoretical Framework.

In this research, the concept of person-organization fit popularized by Lewin (1939) will be applied. Based on Lewin's field theory, the organizational context in which workers and other employees function has an effect on their behavior. Organizational conditions are significantly and continuously impacted by individual employees (Kohn & Schooler, 1982). Employees behave well when they feel that they and the organization are a good fit. Employee engagement occurs, for instance, when a person thinks that their job, organization, group, or supervisor fits their personality and environment well (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005).

According to Chatman (1989) and Kristof-Brown et al. (2005), the concept of "person-organization fit" underlines the significance of the parallels and variances between individuals' distinctive qualities and aims and those of the organizations they work for. Even while it is candidates' knowledge, abilities, and capabilities, the fit between the company and the individual must be thoroughly assessed throughout the hiring process. Conducting job interviews (Sutarjo, 2011).

When staff traits and an organization's environmental traits are in sync, the potential for promoting healthy behaviors in the form of (i) active engagement in work tasks, (ii) increased influences to the company's success, and (iii) amplified demonstrates of organizational citizenship behaviors that support organizational achievement exists (Ünal & Turgut, 2015). Positive organizational and social outcomes may result from a significant emphasis on workplace settings and people, as well as promoting a climate that fosters corporate citizenship activities. Furthermore, this method may assist businesses in advancing their strategic goals and values. raise the likelihood that workers will pursue them freely (Albrecht, 2012; Leskiw & Singh, 2007).

People who share institutional objectives and principles by utilizing efficient communication, proficient leadership, effective performance management, and comprehensive training, individuals can increase their potential to aid and enhance the success of an organization. long-term strategy

because these behavior patterns promote higher levels of job satisfaction (Chatman, 1989; Vilela, González, & Ferrn, 2008). Workers that exhibit organizational citizenship attributes such as compassion, politeness, diligence, sportsmanship, and civic virtue go above and beyond the job requirements (Organ et al., 2006)

2.2 Application of the Theory

Understanding the potential influence of organizational environment aspects on organizational citizenship manners may make it easier to develop the suitable person-organization fit. When the person-organization fit is harmonious and beneficial, the organization's and its employees' performance improves, and change resistance decreases (Castka et al., 2001). The study of organizational citizenship behaviors and organizational environment attributes has opportunity for advancement and extension.

The best fit for this study among the several features of the person-organization fit theory is that understanding individual and organizational traits that impact persons is necessary in order to foresee organizational behavior (Chatman, 1989). Another factor that made this thesis. According to Kristof-Brown et al., (2005) the most viable was the relationship between organizational fit and organizational outcomes

2.3 Empirical Analyses.

Organizational citizenship behavior has been defined in a variety of ways by behavioral scientists. According to Organ (1988, edited in 1997) and others, corporate conduct is defined as follows: flexible individual action that is not immediately or overtly acknowledged by the official incentive system and that, when viewed as a whole, benefits the effective operation of the business. Organ (1997) also stated that because few "in-role" activities guarantee formal compensation, defining corporate citizenship behavior as things that are not officially paid is excessively wide.

Van Dyne et al. defined extra-role behavior (ERB) as "activity that helps the organization and is meant to benefit the organization, is discretionary, and goes beyond established role standards." Thus, organizational citizenship refers to actual, extra-role, pro-social behaviors directed at specific people, groups, or organizations. The organization discreetly endorses these practical methods, for which there are no overt rewards or consequences.

Altruism (Helping): is an altruistic care for others' well-being. Assists those who have been absent or those with heavy workloads.

Courtesy: Take action to try to avoid issues with other employees. Do not violate another person's rights.

Civic virtue: Be present for summits that are not necessary but are thought to be important as a civic virtue. Maintain awareness of any organizational changes.

Conscientiousness: avoids taking further breaks. Observe company policies and procedures even if no one is looking.

Sportsmanship: spends much time whining about unimportant issues. Always concentrate on the negative rather than the positive.

2.4 General Overview: How OCB and OC Relate.

The situation according to Hess (2013), an examination of the healthcare sector finds an analogous situation in the public sector of Somaliland Ministries. According to a study conducted in the United States, the system is unhealthy. Maintaining patient safety and providing high-quality care in a system plagued by drug errors and unnecessary inpatient stays has proven difficult for the failing healthcare sector (Paquet et al.,2012).

Data showing an increase in negative patient outcomes in the organizational environments in which physicians work continued to accumulate in the United States and other countries (Roch, Dubois, & Clarke, 2014). Regardless of their position (Canaday & Hamner, 2008), all medical professionals are affected by labor shortages (Paquet et al., 2012), skyrocketing costs (Hess, 2013), new laws like the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act, and ongoing modification ingenuities. Businesses may generate and manage positive change in the public sector by investigating the association between organizational climate attributes and organizational citizenship practices.

According to Aghaee et al.'s investigation into the links between work burnout, organizational climate, and organizational culture in Iran's Khodro Dizel, organizational climate was beneficial to both OCB and job burnout. Based on the reciprocal relationship between organizational climate and job tiredness, we can assume that OCB grows as a fantastic organizational environment falls and vice versa. (2013) Aghaee and co. Amini M. of the Tehran Municipality used OCB to perform a study on

the work environment among employees of the Tehran Municipality's sports organization. The data revealed a positive and significant link between the organizational climate and OCB. The working climate predicted OCB (Amini, 2012).

2.5 Demographic factors influencing OCB: Individual characteristics

Environment and five OCB features (organizational goals, organizational role) Individual/employee qualities, according to Podsakoff et al., may be predecessors of corporate citizenship actions (2000). Demographic variables, worker aptitudes, worker dispositions, worker conceptions of their tasks, and worker attitudes are among these qualities. According to Nimran (2011), personality traits and extra-role behaviors are connected. Podsakoff et al., on the other hand, discovered no association between demographic characteristics and organizational citizenship practices.

Ahmadizade researched the impact of personality characteristics and corporate culture on OCB. The findings indicate a significant and positive relationship between organizational n, organizational rewards, processes, and intra-organizational communication). The outcomes of the multivariate regression analysis indicate that among organizational climate characteristics and personality traits of proactive personality and openness to experience, organizational objective and communication were the most important predictors of OCB. (Ahmadizade,2012).

Sabzi Pour et al. a study of the relationships between librarians' attitudes, behaviors, and organizational atmosphere. The results of the study showed no relationship between the work environment and the OCB of Iranian public library librarians. 2018 (Sabzi Pour and others)

2.6 Demographic Variables

Age

Researchers have researched both age and organizational citizenship practices. According to Kegans et al., (2012), age and the expression of organizational civic activities do not correlate. The same was true, according to Bahrami et al. (2013), who identified no association between age and corporate citizenship actions. Nimran (2011), on the other hand, discovered a relationship between age and organizational citizenship practices. Nimran claims that a person's organizational citizenship conduct score rises with age.

Gender

Researchers discovered contradictory data about the predicate of organizational citizenship behavior, gender. Extra-role conduct, based on to Ng et al., (2016), is independent to gender. Gender, according to Bahrami et al., (2013), can have an impact on corporate citizenship activities. In their investigation, males were examined more than females.

Pay and Length of Service

The relationship between organizational citizenship behaviors and how long employees stay at a job or in a specific industry has been studied, as well as how salary behaves like a forecaster of organizational citizenship behaviors. Despite Mayfield's observation that eons of practice are clearly connected with corporate citizenship activities, she discovered no relationship between compensation and corporate citizenship behaviors. To be more specific, the length of employment is related to the civic virtues of organizational citizenship (i.e., voluntarily participating in an organization's political existence by attending meetings and being informed about its current state of affairs) (Kegans et al., 2012).

Proficient Advancement/ Specialization

Alternative personal trait studied in relation to corporate citizenship practices is an employee's professional development. Bahrami et al. (2013) discovered no link between education and organizational citizenship actions in their study. Nonetheless, Demirkiran et al., (2016) discovered that leadership support and training can aid to develop organizational citizenship behaviors of healthcare staff. Training and professional development are thus incorporated into employees' activities and obligations even when they are not clearly mentioned in the job description (Jiao et al., 2013).

2.6 Organizational Climate Factors

Organizational climate consideration can increase the possibility of organizational sustainability and competitiveness in any business. In terms of organizational citizenship, citizenship behaviors, performance, and climate and performance, research has shown that there are beneficial correlations between organizational context and behavior (Nimran, 2011). (2014) Shahin and co. Kanten and Ülker piloted one of the most comprehensive studies on organizational climate. The investigators conducted a cross-sectional research in Turkish manufacturing businesses to probe the association between organizational climate and unproductive workers actions. The researchers presented two

surveys to a convenience sample of 204 participants: a 16-item survey examining unproductive practices and a 22-item survey gauging organizational culture. "Counterproductive behaviors" include verbal and physical abuse, insulting others, playing practical jokes on them, acting rudely, squabbling, and favoritism.

Factor analysis, multiple regressions, Cronbach's alpha, and Pearson correlations were all performed by the researchers. The findings, unsurprisingly, revealed a statistically significant inverse link between workplace culture and unproductive behavior. These findings imply that good attitudes are influenced by positive company cultures and goals alignment. Unproductive activities, occur when organizational cultures are seen adversely and do not support employees' aims. The importance of organizational climate can't be overstated (Kanten and Ülker 2013).

Employee Well-Being

The phrase "employee well-being" is used by researchers to define how much an organization loves its employees and cares about their well-being (Patterson et al., (2005). Staff wellbeing can be measured in a range of ways, including regard, care, and concern for staff employees, as well as the establishment of a culture of fairness (Patterson et al., 2005). Because human behavior determines the efficacy and efficiency of operations, companies must grasp the corpus of research on employee well-being (Kegans et al., 2012). Many research on employee happiness and how it influences organizational citizenship have been undertaken behaviors, mostly as a result of workplace culture. Positive workplace interactions help companies retain employees and are another way to improve employee welfare (Lavoie-Tremblay et al., 2010).

Alfonso et al. (2016) investigated the links between these behaviors and emotional intelligence, as well as work life quality and organizational citizenship activities. The investigators also explored (c) the relationship between organizational citizenship practices and emotional intelligence in the workplace, as well as (d) the moderating influence of these behaviors. The findings show a substantial link between generosity, helping others, civic virtue, and emotional intelligence. Working conditions and organizational citizenship activities are also favorably associated.

The Clarity of Staff Positions

According to Gonzalez-Mulé et al. (2016), organizational objective transparency serves as a mediator in the interplay between autonomy and feedback. Based on Gonzalez-Mulé et al. (2016),

this mediating impact between the association of independence and outcome may improve both individual and team performance as well as comprehension of organizational goals. Corporate citizenship acts, such as those required to achieve corporate goals (such as charity, civility, and sportsmanship), will suffer if role expectations are unclear or conflicting (Podsakoff et al., 2000).

Academics argue that in order to encourage **autonomy** inside an organization, employees must be considered in the context of organizational structure. A positive work atmosphere can boost employees' self-esteem (Qadeer & Jaffery, 2014). Work engagement, also known as a positive mental state, is significantly related to psychological empowerment, which is defined as a person's sense of meaningful purpose, level of independence, and belief that work performed has an influence on results. Furthermore, Tremblay and Landreille (2015) discovered that psychological liberation mediates the impacts of information and support sharing. According to Al Sahi Al Zaabi et al., (2016) policies, information exchange, assistance, and training that improve organizational structural empowerment and effectiveness and inspire independent behavior among assisting midwives and nurses and may advance firm's enactment and citizenship manners.

Organizational Goal and Effort

The workforce's efficacy in achieving the organization's goals will enhance if they understand them clearly. They will also be more willing to spend time teaching new staff and be more present at work.

According to Bernstrm et al., (2013) **effort** is the effort that staff do to further the organization's aims. Based on both personal and organizational characteristics, Hitchcock and Stavros (2017) asserted that inspired people work harder to achieve in an organization. Employee effort can vary depending on a variety of personal circumstances. Workers are more likely to actively participate in accomplishing organizational objectives if they believe they are capable of performing a variety of activities aside of their assigned role or if they have a sense of responsibility in the goal-setting process (Phipps-Taylor & Shortell, 2016). The availability and aptness of information to comprehend the consequences of direct care on patients and broader societal health influence doctors' efforts to deliver patient care, teach, and learn (Mohamed & Anisa, 2012).

Based on organizational standpoint, both organizational culture and fit influence employee effort. Congruent individual and organizational principles, according to Ünal and Turgut (2015), can enable fostering positive behavior in the workplace and organizational context. Motivating people to

participate in goal-directed activities is heavily reliant on this alignment. Workers may be willing to put in a lot of work and be dedicated to their professions. Furthermore, they could be willing to use their expertise and skills to help their organizations achieve their goals and use their judgment to help the company succeed (p. 173). Interfaces between staff members at different levels can have an impact on motivation and effort. These relations exist alongside the environment, organizational variables, and human qualities. Leaders become more vigorously involved when employee effort increases, according to Vough et al. (2017).

Communication

Communication is the process by which staff communicate information, make meaning, and establish relationships both inside and outside of businesses. Management can evaluate a variety of communication levels, including those within teams, between employees and external stakeholders, and between employees and management. Because businesses are systems, all kinds of communication should be included when examining the organizational environment.

Honest communication promotes employee relationships when combined with favorable work conditions that include adequate resources and support. (Farzaneh et al. 2014). The degree of communication openness can also be used to evaluate communication. There is a strong relationship between open communication, information sharing among coworkers, and organizational participation (Inanc et al. 2015). Another type of communication that exists in organizations is feedback. Team feedback is fascinating since healthcare organizations are run by a number of teams. Gonzalez-Mulé et al (2016) claims that teams must obtain feedback in order to comprehend company goals and utilize this understanding to direct work efforts. Gonzalez-Mulé et al. discovered that allowing teams to make decisions without consulting them leads to chaos. According to research, the relationship between team autonomy and objective organizational clarity is tempered by performance feedback, which also influences team performance.

Justice and Recompense

According to the study, equality and the dissemination of rewards have an effect on both management and members. The supervisors' fairness demonstrations influence the leader-member dialogue (Sun et al. 2013). Management-staff interaction is defined by degrees of trust, open communication, information sharing, general like, and organizational citizenship habits among

management and staff members. Organizational citizenship activities are increasing. when leaders provide rewards that are relevant to their workforce, when employees think that leaders have some control over how rewards are given out and when rewards are tied to performance (Podsakoff et al. 2000).

Pay

According to Sulistiyani (2014), whereas private sector employees receive numerous incentives in addition to their pay, government employees' income is primarily centered on their wages. Because they get equivalent compensation to others, government employees may withhold OCB and do minimal effort to meet organizational needs. According to Lee and Sabharwal (2016), the efficacy of wage as a driver of JS differs by sector. According to Unal (2013), the factors of JS caused by money and the job itself would positively influence the exhibition of politeness.

Promotion and OCB Dimensions

According to Tzafrir and Hareli (2009), employees who believe it will be difficult to advance have higher OCB than those who believe it will be straightforward. OCB in the workplace is defined by Boulanger (2013) as actions that promote worker productivity without measuring performance or compensating individuals. According to a study conducted on the managers of an Ankara-based public bank, progress and job satisfaction will have an impact on OCB (Unal, 2013). This is consistent with Ngadiman & Ratmawati's (2013) study of lecturers, which discovered that promotion and actual work are the most important factors impacting OCB.

2,7 Organization Citizenship Behavior Dimensions

Organization Citizenship Behavior is defined as supporting acts that are neither overtly encouraged nor prohibited by the organization, according to Van Dyne et al. (1995). Corporate Social Responsibility We do not include dysfunctional or noncompliant behavior in our definition of behavior, nor do we consider pro-social actions enforced by the company as performance requirements.

Civic Duty: According to the findings of a study by Safarzadeh et al., "innovative organizational climate and job excitement with civic virtue among female employees in an industrial organization in Ahvaz City," there is a affirmative and important link between these two parameters.

Altruism: Employees that display corporate citizenship behavior usually have moral character or moral judgment. Peer evaluations of altruistic organizational citizenship behavior on 96 American nurses conducted by Wagner et al. (2000) revealed that younger participants were more susceptible to contextual factors. Among the elder participants, the dispositional variable of moral judgment was an extraordinary predictor of altruistic Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Moral leadership will be valued by everyone on the team. This can only be done by cultivating a society that values moral judgment.

Sportsmanship: Barrick and Mount (1991), asserts that public-sector firms have more responsive personnel than private-sector businesses. Workers who can compromise behave more professionally. Even by itself, "agreeableness" is an important characteristic. Individuals with elevated levels of agreeableness are more likely to engage in helping activities than those with low levels of this attribute, according to John and Srivastava (1999). Elanain's (2007) discovery that there is a strong positive association between agreeableness and organizational citizenship activity lends credence to the hypothesis that agreeableness characterizes organizational citizenship behavior.

Mindfulness: Cilla Michael's mindfulness research was titled "Study of the Connection between OCB and Organizational Environment for Creativity Among Students at Metropolitan University in Northern California." He discovered that OCBs were frequently related to how innovative the workers perceived the business culture to be. Employees who work in creative environments have strong social connections and internal motivation. A thriving business culture can also inspire creativity among its employees. 2021 (Cilla Michael)

2.8 Summary of Literature Review

Organizational citizenship behaviors were the dependent variable under investigation, and researchers uncovered both antecedents and consequences of this behavior. A review of previous research was offered, as well as a critical study of the independent variable organizational climate. Employee well-being, autonomy, organizational goals, effort, communication, and rewards were all weighed against the independent variable.

The examination of the research literature revealed that a variety of factors, including as personality traits, duties and positions, organizational attributes, and leadership, may have an influence on firm's citizenship manners. Other concepts that can be used to evaluate corporate citizenship activities include altruism, sportsmanship consciousness civic virtue and civility

The propagation of diverse organizational climate components leads to misperception and emphasizes the importance of a well-designed model. Inconsistent results were discovered in the study that was undertaken to investigate the association between organizational citizenship and climate practices. The most favorable and significant variables to consider, as well as the best approaches to assess the organizational environment, are contested subjects (Liou & Cheng, 2010). Regardless of this dispute, the impact of organizational citizenship initiatives on corporate environment is a constant subject in the examined literature. There is a gap in the literature regarding the organizational climate domains that have a significant impact on the domains that significantly influence the organizational citizenship behaviors of public sector employees, particularly the human affairs sector (Patterson et al., 2005).

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter contains the study area, research design, target population, sample size and sampling procedure, data collection methods, data type and sources, validity and reliability test, data analysis and ethical considerations.

3.1 Study Area

The study will be conducted in Hargeisa Somaliland especially at the Ministry of Agriculture. In fulfilling all of the responsibilities as enshrined in Article 17 of the Executive Regulation No. 01/2018, the mandate of the Ministry of Agriculture encompasses all aspects of agricultural development ranging from agricultural resource utilization and management, crop production, agro-processing, marketing and pest and disease control. Severely damaged by the civil war and with unpredicted weather events disrupting Somaliland agricultural production, the industry is slowly regaining strength.

Governance for crop and animal production is divided between the Ministry of Agricultural Development and the Ministry of Livestock. As stated in the National Agriculture Strategic Plan (NASP) the regulation No. 01/2018, lists the following mandates and responsibilities for the Ministry of Agricultural development:

3.2 Research Design

This study will adopt a quantitative cross-sectional research design to identify potential relationships between organizational climate variables and organizational citizenship behaviors.

A survey design that gathers facts to discover, clarify and describe incidences, distribution, or interrelationships without manipulating variables. According to Campbell and Stanley (1963), cross-sectional methods are used to collect data at one-point data at one point in time. This study will use a cross-sectional design because it provides the ability to collect a large amount of data quickly at one point in time (Sedgwick, 2014).

3.3 Target Population

This study targets all employees of the Ministry of Agriculture. There are different departments in the ministry namely Admin and Finance, Planning and Coordination, Production and Food Security,

Plant Protection, Research and Extension, Human Resource, Land and Water, Meteorology, Transport and Mechanization and ICT.

The review of the current organizational structure and the list of staff and payroll revealed that there are 95 members of staff in the Ministry of Agriculture's Hargeisa office. This complement comprises of 1 Director General, 10 departmental Directors, 28 Deputy Directors/Head of Sections, 3 technical staff, 6 regional coordinators, 23 clerks and secretaries, and 19 drivers and messengers, (CSSP SEPTEMBER., 2021)

3.4 Sample size and Sampling Procedure

Sample Size

This study will adopt a census method since the employees are less than 100. This means that all employees will be part of the sample. Therefore, the sample size is 95 respondents

Procedure

The researcher used the Census Method of Data Collection which is trustworthy and Accurate. the results obtained through the census method of data collection are highly trustworthy and accurate. Because this strategy entails studying each and every item in the population, so, the results will reliable and accurate. It is also less biased because the researcher does not have to collect sample items for the study and must study the entire population. thus, the information gathered will be quite in-depth and more meaningful.

3.5 Data Collection Methods

The main method of data collection will be a Self-administered questionnaire that will be distributed to the officials in the officials in different departments of MOA to provide answers. The questionnaire will be semi structured with both closed and open-ended questions. This instrument was purposely selected because it seeks personal views of the respondents and thus enable the respondents to use their knowledge in providing a wide range of data as they are never shy away.

This will be followed by sample selection based on the departments as explained in the sampling technique above. For effective approach of the respondents, the researcher will make a self-introduction and request for consent of the respondents in taking part in the exercise. Questionnaires will then be distributed to the selected and willing respondents from the sample.

3.6 Data type and Sources

The researcher will use the data from both primary and secondary data sources. The primary data will be collected through distributing questionnaire to the respondents to get the information required in the study.

The researcher is going to collect the primary data in a form of closed ended questionnaires because it is easy to apply as most respondents will be well educated and can fill in the questions easily or with little guidance. Open ended questions will also be used in order to give the respondents a chance for in-depth opinions. According to Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003 questionnaire is used when factual information is desired.

The secondary data is collecting from existed documents or books. The sources include: text books, library sources, field research resources, the internet and other materials (such as academic journals, newspapers, etc.)

3.7 Validity and Reliability Test

Validity of the instrument is assuring through expert judgment and the researcher will make sure that the coefficient of validity to be at least 70%. The researcher will make consultations with the supervisor for expert knowledge on questionnaire construction, After the assessment of the questionnaire, the necessary adjustments will make bearing in mind the objectives of the study.

Reliability is measure the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results or data after repeated trials (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). Reliability of the instrument is established through a test-retest technique. The researcher conducting a pre-test of the instrument on group of subjects and waiting one week then administered the same test to the same subjects a second time.

3.8 Data Analysis

The quantitative information is involved data from the questionnaires only. The data from the field is raw for proper interpretation. It is therefore vital to put it into order and structure it, so as to drive meaning and information from it. The raw data obtained from questionnaires is cleaned, sorted and coded. The coded data is entered into the Computer, checking and statistically analyzing using the statistical package for social scientists (SPSS) software package to generate descriptive and inferential statistics. Data analysis on the first to the third objective will be analyzed used multiple regression analysis.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

The researcher is going to carry out the study with full knowledge and authorization of the responsible authority. First, the researcher will obtain a letter of introduction from the School of Graduate Studies, administrative office about the research topic and will be asked the permission from the administrative bodies of the ministry of Agriculture to conduct the research. Second, the researcher will tell the targeted organizations the purpose of the study to the respondents and ensured voluntary participation, as it is only for academic purpose with full confidentiality. The cover letter of the questionnaire will be included the purpose of the study and about confidentiality and necessary instructions for respondents.

CHAPTER FOUR

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter outlines the result and findings of the study. It also gives the discussions and summary of the findings. The information in this chapter is derived from the responses of the people we gathered information from by distributing the questionnaires.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

This section analysis the socio demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 4.1 socio-demographic profile

Profile of Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
Gender of the respondent		
Male	82	86.3%
Female	13	36.4%
Total	95	100.0
Age of the respondent		
20-30	13	13.7%
31-40	40	42.1%
51-60	42	44.2%
Total	95	100.0%
Education level of the respondent		
Diploma	22	23.2%
Bachelor	73	76.8%
Total	95	100.0%
Experience of the respondent		
1-2 years	27	28.4%
3-4 years	4	4.2%

5-6 years	64	67.4%
Total	95	100.0%
Marital status of the respondent		
Married	72	75.8%
Single	23	24.2%
Total	95	100.0%

Source: primary data (2023)

Table 4.1 shows that 86.3% of the respondents were male while only 13.7% were female. This indicates that majority of the employees in MOA are male.

In addition, table 4.1 Clearly describes that very few respondents were between 20-30 years of age shown by 13.7%. However, the elderly between 51-60 years are slightly higher 44.2% than the working age group 31-40 which is 42.1%. This shows that majority of the employees in MOA are a mature group of people with very few youths.

Furthermore, table 4.1 uncovered About the education level of the employees, 23.2% have diploma while 76.8% have bachelor's degree. This result shows that majority of the employees in MOA have Sufficient level of education to perform duties entrusted to them.

Table 4.1 also indicates the number of years in working experience for the employees, that shows 67.4% of the respondents have been working at MOA for more than 5yrs. A smaller percentage were in the 1-2 years of working which is 28.4%. A very small percentage 4.2% were in their 3rd to 4th year of experience. This shows there was probably a gap in number of employees joining the Ministry and those continuing to work after 2 yrs.

Moreover, table 4.1 describes that 75.8% of the employees are married, while only 24.2 % are single. This is consistent with the age results since most of the employees are above the age of 30 which means they are married and can manage their responsibilities well.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

Objective one of the study was to describe the level of organization climate and the organization citizenship behavior at MOA Hargeisa. This objective was achieved by analyzing data using mean and standard deviation. The table below shows the interpretation guide for the Likert scale used in the questionnaire

Table 4.2 Interpretation Guide (Numerical Guide)

No	Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
5	4.26 – 5.05	Strongly Agree	Very high
4	3.46 – 4.25	Agree	High
3	2.66 – 3.45	Neutral	Normal
2	1.86 – 2.65	Disagree	Low
1	1.00 – 1.85	Strongly Disagree	Very low

4.2.1 Level of Organization Climate

Table 4.3 Level of Organization Climate at the Ministry of Agriculture.

The level of Organizational climate	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Rewards				
I feel my pay is fair for the work I do	95	1.46	.823	Very low
The current level of benefits provided by the MOAD satisfies me	95	1.96	.202	Low
I am satisfactorily compensated in the MOAD as compared to employee in the other ministries with similar responsibility	95	2.19	.490	Low
I feel that rewards and benefits are handled in the same way for all employees	95	1.68	1.231	Very low
Mean		1.82		Very Low
Communication				
I receive all the information I need to carry out my work.	95	1.89	1.627	Low
Communication channels in the MOAD are always open.	95	1.72	.453	Very Low
News affecting the MOAD are communicated effectively	95	1.35	.632	Very Low
I receive sufficient updates on matters of importance in my department.	95	1.99	.230	Low

I have the opportunity to share my ideas with my department.	95	1.05	.268	Very Low
Mean		1.60		Very Low
Promotion				
I believe that I will have career growth opportunities in the MOAD	95	1.25	.437	Very Low
My promotion and career path are clear for me.	95	2.62	.587	Low
I understand the criteria that I need to meet my promotion path in the MOAD.	95	1.98	.252	Low
I can develop my career within the MOAD because there is an adequate system for Career progression in the ministry.	95	1.08	.279	Very Low
Employees are promoted fairly in the MOAD system	95	1.91	.294	Low
Mean		1.77		Very Low
Autonomy				
I feel free to suggest changes within my job role	95	1.47	.836	Very Low
I have flexibility in the way I get my job done	95	2.19	.445	Low
I have the necessary supplies and equipment to do my job well	95	1.28	.498	Very Low
I feel my decisions are respected and followed	95	2.41	.881	Low
I'm comfortable with the responsibilities that I have right now	95	1.27	.448	Very Low
Mean		1.72		Very Low
Organizational Goals				
Goals and ambitions of the MOAD are clear to me	95	2.85	.505	Average
I consider that my work is important for the MOAD to reach its goals	95	2.88	.353	Average
My immediate co-workers are committed to the organization's goals	95	2.61	.624	Low
I believe that the MOAD is able to reach its goals and objectives	95	2.64	.544	Low
Mean	2.75			Average
Overall Mean	1.93			Low

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Table 4.3 above shows us the findings of the level of Organization Climate at the Ministry of Agriculture. Upon analysis of the rewards system, effective communication, clear and understandable organization goals, and the availability of promotion and autonomy, the overall level of organization climate at MOA was found to be Low (Overall mean = 1.93).

In terms of rewards, majority were not satisfied with their current pay ($\mu=1.96$, $STD=0.202$) while the others felt that the pay was not fair for the work they were doing. Most of them also felt that the rewards and benefits were not handled fairly in the department ($\mu=1.68$, $STD=1.231$). Overall, majority of the respondents strongly disagreed with the rewards and benefits they were receiving at MOA ($\mu=1.82$, I=Very low).

About effective communication, the respondents said that communication channels in the MOAD are not open ($\mu=1.72$, $STD=0.453$, I=very low) and they do not receive all the information they need to carry out their work ($\mu=1.89$, $STD=1.627$, I= low). Majority also confirmed that important updates are not communicated effectively ($\mu=1.99$, $STD=0.230$) and worse of all, majority strongly disagreed with having the opportunity to share their ideas with the department ($\mu=1.05$, $STD=0.268$, I=very low). Overall, there are very poor communication strategies in the departments at the MOA ($\mu=1.60$, I=Very low).

Majority strongly disagreed with the promotion situation at MOA. A lot of respondents complained that employees are not promoted fairly ($\mu=1.91$, $STD= 0.294$), while most of them did not see a career growth with the ministry ($\mu=1.25$, $STD=0.437$, I=very low). Overall, the availability and knowledge of promotion opportunities at the MOA was very low ($\mu=1.77$, I=very low). This result probably explains why most of the respondents dropped out of the ministry after 2 years of working there

The level of autonomy at the MOA is very low ($\mu=1.72$, I=very low). The level of being free to suggest any changes was found to be very low ($\mu=1.47$, $STD=0.836$, I=very low) and did not have flexibility in the way they did their jobs. Majority responded that they do not have the necessary supplies and equipment's necessary to do their jobs ($\mu=1.28$, $STD=0.498$, I=very low) and some were not sure if their decisions were being respected.

When respondents were asked whether the organizational goals were clear, there were mixed reactions. Majority of the respondents were reserved and neutral about that situation ($\mu=2.75$, I =average). The goals and ambitions of MOAD were clear up to an average level to the employees ($\mu=2.85$, $STD=0.505$), the commitment levels of coworkers were found to be low and majority were not sure if their work contributed to achieving the goal of the organization ($\mu=2.88$, $STD=0.353$, I =average).

4.2.2 Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Table 4.3 Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational Citizenship Behavior	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Altruism				
I help others who have heavy workloads	95	1.99	.372	Very low
I am always ready to lend a helping hand to those around me	95	1.36	.651	Very low
I help others who have been absent	95	1.99	.273	Low
I am willing to help others who have workrelated problems	95	2.55	.896	Low
I help orient new people even if it is not required from me	95	3.38	1.002	High
Mean	2.25			Low
Conscientiousness / Mindfulness				
I am one of the most conscientious/reliable employees complete work on time	95	2.93	.419	Average
I believe in giving an honest day's work for an honest day's pay (honest and dedicated person)	95	2.46	.885	High
My attendance at work is above the normal requirement	95	3.33	.972	High
I do not take extra breaks	95	3.17	1.277	Average
I obey organization/institution rules and regulations even when no one is watching.	95	4.06	1.413	Very high
I do not express resentment with any changes introduced by management	95	2.66	.576	Average
Mean	3.10			Average
Sportsmanship				
I do not consume a lot of time complaining about trivial matters	95	2.73	.535	Average
I do not tend to make "Mountains out of molehills"	95	2.94	.457	Average
I always focus on the positive side rather than the negative side	95	2.75	.652	Average

I do not always find fault with what the organization is doing	95	1.99	.425	Low
Mean		2.60		Low
Courtesy				
I try to avoid creating problems for coworkers	95	3.33	1.372	High
I consider the impact of my actions on coworkers	95	3.69	1.585	High
I do not abuse the rights of others	95	4.12	1.613	Very high
I take steps to try to prevent problems with other workers	95	2.79	.600	Average
I am mindful of how my behavior affects other people's jobs	95	3.27	.972	Average
Mean		3.44		Average
Civic Virtue				
I keep abreast (well-informed) of changes in the organization	95	2.01	.342	Low
I attend meetings that are not mandatory but are considered important	95	2.89	.449	Average
I attend functions that are not required by help the institutional image.	95	2.00	.326	Low
I read and keep up with institutional announcements, memos and so on.	95	3.84	1.788	High
Mean		2.69		Average
Overall Mean		2.82		Average

Source: Primary Data (2023)

The table above shows the findings on the level of OCB in MOA. When the factors of OCB were analyzed, that is Altruism, Conscientiousness / Mindfulness, Sportsmanship, Courtesy and, Civic Virtue, the level of OCB was found to be on average (overall mean=2.82, I=Average). This means that it was neither high nor low but rather at a normal level. However, altruism and sportsmanship were found to be low. Under altruism, the ability to help others who had heavy workloads ($\mu=1.99$, $STD=0.372$), absent ($\mu=1.99$, $STD=0.273$), or having work related problems ($\mu=2.55$, $STD=0.896$), was found to be very low. On the contrary, the level of helping in orientation of new people even if it is not required from them to do so was found to be very high ($\mu=3.38$, $STD=1.002$). Therefore, in overall, the level of altruism was found to be low ($\mu=2.25$, I=low). These results indicate that majority of the employees at MOA do not have the willingness to help others in the department.

Under sportsmanship, the level of ability of staffs to adapt to hardships at work place, without any verbal or formal complaining was found to be low ($\mu=2.60$, I=low). The level of complaining about trivial matters ($\mu=2.73$, $STD=0.535$), magnifying issues at work place ($\mu=2.94$, $STD=0.457$), and focusing on the positive rather than negative ($\mu=2.75$, $STD=0.652$), was found to be on an average level. In addition, majority of the employees usually find fault with what the organization is doing ($\mu=1.99$, $STD=0.425$).

The level of conscientiousness was found to be on average ($\mu=3.10$, I=Average). The level of obeying organization rules and regulations was very high ($\mu=4.06$, $STD=1.413$), attendance at work was also high ($\mu=3.33$, $STD=0.972$) and majority believed they were mindful employees in the organization ($\mu=2.93$, $STD=0.419$). These results indicate that majority of employees at MOA are conscious and mindful of their actions.

On the other hand, the level of courtesy was found to be on average ($\mu=3.44$, I=Average). Majority of the employees try to avoid creating problems for coworkers ($\mu=3.33$, $STD=1.372$), they are considerate about the impact of their actions on other coworkers ($\mu=3.69$, $STD=1.585$) and do not abuse the rights of others ($\mu=4.12$, $STD=1.613$). These results indicate that the employees at MOA exhibit a high level of courtesy

Finally, an average level of exercising civic virtue was found within the employees of MOA ($\mu=2.69$, I=Average). The level of reading and keeping up with institutional announcements, memos and so on was high ($\mu=3.84$, $STD=1.788$). However, majority were not well informed about changes in the organization ($\mu=2.01$, $STD=0.342$), and did not attend functions that were not required just to help boost the institutional image ($\mu=2.00$, $STD=0.326$). Majority did not feel the need to attend meetings that were not mandatory ($\mu=2.89$, $STD=0.449$). These results shows that the employees at MOA did not feel the need to exercise their civic virtue or the organization and thus it was low.

4.3 Inferential Statistics

4.3.1 Correlation Analysis

Objective two of the study was to determine the association between organization climate dimensions and the OCB of staff at the MOA. This objective was achieved by carrying out a correlation analysis between the computed DV and IV. The table below shows the results.

Table 4.4 Correlation analysis matrix findings

		Organizational climate	Organizational citizenship behaviors
Organizational climate	Pearson Correlation	1	.847**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	95	95
Organizational citizenship behaviors	Pearson Correlation	.847**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	95	95
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

This table analyses the strength of correlation between OCB and Organization climate. The table shows there is a very strong, positive and significant correlation between the two variables, ($r=0.847$, $Sig=0.000$). This means that as the value of organization climate goes up, then the value of OCB also goes up. These results are in collaboration with the descriptive results where by, since the value of OC of MOA is very low, the OCB of the employees has also been seen to be very low. These findings are also inconsistency with other scholars such as Aghaee *et al*, Safarzade *et al*, Shaymy *et al*, Zamanim Moghadam *et al*, and Amini.

4.3.2 Regression Analysis

Objective three of the study was to explore the influence of organization climate on OCB of staff at the MOA Hargeisa. This objective was achieved by carrying out a multiple regression analysis of the variables. The table below shows the results.

Table 4.5: Multiple regression analysis findings

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.895	4.002		.224	.824
	Goals	.272	.106	.115	2.576	.010
	Rewards	.969	.195	.782	4.961	.000
	Autonomy	.419	1.058	.186	.396	.693
	Welfare	.722	1.139	.415	.634	.528

	Communication	.569	.172	.684	3.291	.001
a. Dependent Variable: Computed OCB						

The table shows the regression analysis on the predictors of OCB. From the table, two variables, Autonomy (B=0.419, t=0.396, p=0.693) and Welfare (B=0.722, t=0.634, p=0.528) are insignificant and cannot influence the value of OCB.

On the other hand, organizational goals, rewards and effective communication have a positive and significant influence on OCB of MOA employees. The biggest factor that influences OCB is the availability of rewards and benefits, (B=0.969, t=4.961, p=0.000). This means that an increase in the value of rewards can influence the increase of OCB among employees up to 96.9%. This is closely followed by effective communication (B=0.569, t=3.291, p=0.001) in the MOA. This means that if communication strategies are improved, there is a 56.9% chance of increasing the OCB of employees in MOA. Last but not least, the organizational goals have a positive and significant influence on OCB (B=0.272, t=2.576, p=0.010). This means that if the goals are set clearly and employees are aware of their role in achieving these goals, then the OCB is likely to increase with 27.2%.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter gives conclusions and recommendations of the study

5.1 Conclusion

5.1.1 Social demographic profile

From the results the MOA employs more males than females. This is probably associated with the gender imbalance in Hargeisa that women are still gaining the right to hold public offices. Conversely, many women view agriculture as a strenuous and manly work and therefore do not undertake this kind of study. Most respondents were also married and above the age of 30. Majority of these respondents have a bachelor's degree from the universities. The elderly respondents above the age of 40 had more experience compared to the youth who were in their 1st to 2nd year of working.

5.1.2 Objective one: To determine the level of organization climate and the organization citizenship behavior at MOA Hargeisa.

The overall level of organization climate at MOA was found to be Low (Overall mean = 1.93). Majority of the respondents strongly disagreed with the rewards and benefits they were receiving at MOA ($\mu=1.82$, I=Very low). Overall, there are very poor communication strategies in the departments at the MOA ($\mu=1.60$, I=Very low). The availability and knowledge of promotion opportunities at the MOA was very low ($\mu=1.77$, I=very low) and low levels of autonomy were confirmed at the MOA ($\mu=1.72$, I=very low) since majority did not feel free to voice their ideas nor was the work flexible. Finally, when respondents were asked whether the organizational goals were clear, there were mixed reactions. A significant number of the respondents established that the organizational goals and ambitions were clear up to an average level however, some had no idea if what they were doing was contributing towards achieving them. The level of knowledge of clear Organizational goals was concluded to be average ($\mu=2.75$, I=average).

On the other hand, Organizational citizenship behavior dimensions received mixed reactions. The level of OCB was found to be on average (overall mean=2.82, I=Average). This means that it was neither high nor low but rather at a normal level. However, altruism and sportsmanship are low at MOA. The level of altruism was found to be low ($\mu=2.25$, I=low) indicating that majority of the employees at MOA do not have the willingness to help others in the department. Sportsmanship is also low ($\mu=2.60$, I=low) indicating that the staffs have a low ability to adapt to hardships at work place, without any verbal or formal complaining. There is an average level of conscientiousness among the employees ($\mu=3.10$, I=Average) indicating that majority of employees at MOA are conscious and mindful of their actions. The level of courtesy is also average ($\mu=3.44$, I=Average) indicating that the employees at MOA exhibit a high level of courtesy. On the contrary, an average level of exercising civic virtue was found within the employees of MOA ($\mu=2.69$, I=Average). The mean is on the lower side meaning the employees at MOA do not feel the need to exercise their civic virtue or the organization

5.1.3 Objective two: To determine the association between organization climate dimensions and the OCB of staff at the MOA.

There is a very high, positive and significant correlation between the two variables, ($r=0.847$, $t=0.000$). This means that as the value of organization climate goes up, then the value of OCB also goes up. This is clearly explained by the situation at MOA as seen from objective one. Since the value of the organization climate is very low, consequently, the OCB of employees at MOA is also very low. For example, most employees said that they couldn't associate a career growth at the ministry and consequently most of them left after 2 years of working there.

5.1.4 Objective three: To explore the influence of organization climate on OCB of staff at the MOA Hargeisa.

From the multiple regression analysis, organizational goals, rewards and effective communication have a positive and significant influence on OCB of MOA employees. The biggest factor that influences OCB is the availability of rewards and benefits, which can increase the value of OCB by 96.9%, closely followed by effective communication which can influence the value by 56.9% in the MOA and finally the organizational goals which can increase the level of OCB by 27.2%. The study can therefore infer that the employees would uphold their civic virtue of the organization if the reward they received for it is very low and unsatisfactory.

5.2 Recommendations

Following the findings of this study, the researcher recommends the following:

The leaders of the Ministry of Agriculture should establish a fair rewards and benefits system as mentioned in the results of the analysis the rewards and benefits are not handled fairly in the departments. Overall, a very high percentage of the respondents 83.4% are not satisfied at all with their level of reward and benefits they receive at the ministry.

Secondly, leaders of the ministry should develop effective communication system that can enable all staff to get essential information concerning their daily tasks. As discussed in the analysis section, there is a poor communication at the departments, important updates are not communicated effectively and worse of all, a great number of the staff don't have the opportunity to share their ideas with higher officials.

Effective promotion system and clear career growth path should be initiated by the leaders of the ministry as majority of the employees complained the lack of fair promotion and career growth at the ministry.

Clear goals and ambitions also should be stated clearly, as a fair number of the staff complained that organizational goals and ambitions are not clear for them.

For any organization to succeed, feeling autonomy is essential for the staff. The higher officials of the ministry and heads of the departments should allow employees to feel autonomy, sense their suggestions are respected and comfortable with their responsibilities.

In conclusion, I propose that future scholars and researchers to broaden the scope of this paper and conduct a thorough study on the broader topic of civil service institutions and ministries in Somaliland to obtain comprehensive knowledge of the impact of organizational climate on the organizational citizenship behavior of employees in public institutions in Somaliland.

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APPENDICES

5.3 APPENDIX I: INTRODUCTORY LETTER

INTRODUCTORY LETTER

Dear Respondent,

My name is Mohamed Osman Ibrahim, graduating a Master's Degree in Human Resource Management at University of Hargeisa. I am conducting a research on **“The influence of organizational climate on organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees of public institutions in Somaliland, the case of Somaliland Ministry of Agriculture in Hargeisa”**.

I have developed this questionnaire to collect the information that relate to this study and you have been selected to take part in this research by faithfully completing the attached questionnaire.

Please note that your responses will be kept confidential.

Yours faithfully,

Mohamed Osman Ibrahim, (Researcher)

5.4 QUESTIONNAIRE

APPENDIX A: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Make tick (✓) to your answer in the box

1. Gender

Male Female

2. Age

20-30 31-40 41-50 51-50.

60 and above

3. Highest Level of Education

Secondary

Diploma

Bachelor.

Masters

Other (please specify): _____

4. Working Experience

1-2 years. 3-4 years 5-6 years 7-8 years 9 years and above

5. Marital Status

Married Single

APPENDIX B: ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE QUESTIONNAIRE

Please respond to the following questions by circling the best-fitting number. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions. It is important that you respond to each question. Thank you for your time.

1 = Strongly Disagree

2 = Disagree

3 = Neutral

4 = Agree

5 = Strongly Agree

	Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA
	Organizational Climate Dimensions	1	2	3	4	5
	Rewards					
1	I feel my pay is fair for the work I do.					
2	The current level of benefits provided by the MOAD satisfies me.					
3	I am satisfactorily compensated in the MOAD as compared to employees in other ministries with similar responsibilities.					
4	I feel that rewards and benefits are handled in the same way for all employees.					
	Communication					
5	I receive all the information I need to carry out my work.					
6	News affecting the MOAD are communicated effectively throughout the departments.					
7	I receive sufficient updates on matters of importance in my department.					
8	I have the opportunity to share my ideas with my department.					
9	I receive all the information I need to carry out my work.					
	Promotion					
10	I believe that I will have career growth opportunities in the MOAD					
11	My promotion and career path are clear for me.					
12	There is an adequate system for Career progression in the ministry.					
13	Employees are promoted fairly in the MOAD system					
14	I believe that I will have career growth opportunities in the MOAD					
	Autonomy					
15	I feel free to suggest changes within my job role					
16	I have the necessary supplies and equipment to do my job well					
17	I feel my decisions are respected and followed					
18	I'm comfortable with the responsibilities that I have right now					
19	I feel free to suggest changes within my job role					
	Organizational Goals					
20	Goals and ambitions of the MOAD are clear to me					
21	I consider that my work is important for the MOAD to reach its goals					
22	I believe that the MOAD is able to reach its goals and objectives					

23	I believe that the MOAD's objectives can help me achieve my personal goals.						
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APPENDIX C: ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR QUESTIONNAIRE

Please respond to the following questions by circling the best-fitting number. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions. It is important that you respond to each question. Thank you for your time.

#	Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA
	Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Dimensions	1	2	3	4	5
	Altruism					
1	I help others who have heavy workloads					
2	I am always ready to lend a helping hand to those around me					
3	I help others who have been absent					
4	I am willing to help others who have work-related problems					
5	I help orient new people even if it is not required from me					
	Conscientiousness / Mindfulness					
6	I am one of the most conscientious/reliable employees who complete work on time					
7	I believe in giving an honest day's work for an honest day's pay (honest and dedicated person)					
8	My attendance at work is above the normal requirement					
9	I do not take extra breaks					
10	I obey organization/institution rules and regulations even when no one is watching.					
	Sportsmanship					
12	I do not consume a lot of time complaining about trivial (unimportant) matters					
13	I do not tend to make "Mountains out of molehills" (not very upset over small problems)					
14	I always focus on the positive side rather than the negative side					
15	I do not always find fault with what the organization is doing					
	Courtesy					
16	I try to avoid creating problems for co-workers					
17	I consider the impact of my actions on co-workers					
18	I do not abuse the rights of others					
19	I take steps to try to prevent problems with other workers					
20	I am mindful of how my behaviour affects other people's jobs					
	Civic Virtue					

21	I keep abreast (well-informed) of changes in the organization					
22	I attend meetings that are not mandatory but are considered important					
23	I attend functions that are not required but help the institutional image.					
24	I read and keep up with institutional announcements, memos and so on.					

1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

5.4.2 Appendix III: Time Frame

<i>Activity description</i>	<i>Feb 2023</i>	<i>March 2023</i>	<i>April 2023</i>	<i>May 2023</i>	<i>June 2023</i>	<i>July 2023</i>
<i>Chapter One</i>						
<i>Chapter Two</i>						
<i>Chapter Three</i>						
<i>Proposal Defence</i>						
<i>Chapter Four</i>						
<i>Chapter Five</i>						
<i>Submission of Hardcopy</i>						29th July